

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Navigating the Future with AI-Powered Insights: Challenges and Strategies for Digital Evolution

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Abstract

Objectives: The purpose of this study is to investigate how AI may improve data-centric procedures and strengthen economic ties in emerging nations. It also looks at how ethics and readiness for AI adoption affect strategic governance and policymaking, as well as how they mediate the spread of knowledge. **Methods:** Data were obtained from 350 respondents in the public and private sectors via interviews and online questionnaires, with 302 valid replies being used for analysis. Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess the reliability of constructs relevant to AI adoption, knowledge management, and decision-making; all of them above the 0.7 threshold, showing good internal consistency. **Findings:** According to the study, when accompanied by organizational preparedness and ethical governance, the deployment of AI greatly improves corporate decision-making, efficiency, and knowledge transformation. The adoption of AI and its successful, responsible integration into corporate systems are closely related, as demonstrated by mediation effects, to readiness and ethical responsibility. **Novelty:** Within the process of transforming AI knowledge, this study presents two new mediating constructs: ethical responsibility in AI application and corporate readiness to integrate AI. Additionally, it highlights how important ethical governance and organizational readiness are to the effective and responsible deployment of AI across businesses.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Ethical AI Governance; Industry 4.0; Predictive Analytics; Machine Learning

1 Introduction and Literature

The integration of AI-driven analytics, forecasting, and decision-making interfaces is reshaping business operations, economic strategies, and public management. The enhancement of effectiveness, agility, and precision in decision making by AI is, however, accompanied by ethical, regulatory, and legal interpretive challenges that require resolution toward AI accountability. Data driven decision making has changed from being an efficiency tool to a necessity dictated by changes in market and consumer behavior. Businesses have very little time to adapt to changes in the market, customer expectations, and emerging opportunities. The results of AI powered analytics make it

possible for businesses to gather and process information through real time analysis, which enhances strategic agility. Applying AI and ML technologies makes it possible to derive actionable insights from a company's large and complex data sets, boosting productivity, growth, and effective governance.

The integration of AI into data analytics enables companies to shift from conventional passive reporting to instantaneous active decision making. Google Analytics 4, Adobe Experience Platform, and AI enhanced business Intelligence tools provide unparalleled capabilities for analyzing consumer behavior, optimizing marketing campaigns, and audience segmentation. These AI systems no longer need human analysts to drill the most valuable associations and insights, profoundly changing how businesses process data and how they cope with ceaseless market change. AI-powered business analytics has offered companies newer benefits alongside persistent problems. Enhancing the predicted accuracy and addressing data secrecy issues tends to limit the ideal functioning of AI models.

The dominating expansion of AI technology provides new opportunities for automated and intelligent decision making in Industry 4.0 frameworks. Industry 4.0, as the digital transformation of industrial processes, is described as cyber-physical systems integration, big data analytics, and the automation of the Internet of Things. This is done by further incorporating AI into the existing decision support systems (DSS); these systems help industries obtain operational data, detect inefficiencies in real-time, and manage business processes to achieve more efficient workflows. In this context, AI enhances productivity by anticipating and mitigating downtimes, thus improving maintenance, supply chain management, and quality control functions⁽¹⁾. The integration of predictive analytics and AI has altered the industrial efficiency paradigm by relying on existing data to forecast changes and reallocate resources accordingly⁽²⁾. In spite of that, there is a guarantee that AI is used ethically and responsibly in the manufacturing and logistics industries, so dilemmas and practical limitations need to be addressed.

Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa (BRICS) are continuously developing both domestically and internationally while accounting for a large share of the global GDP. These countries, together, are actively leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) powered policies and tools to achieve sustainable economic growth⁽³⁾. The introduction of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning has offered unparalleled benefits in the domain of data analysis, resource allocation, trade policy modification, and more⁽⁴⁾. Although AI has offered some benefits, it appears that most of its potential is still untapped because governance problems, ethical application of AI, and sovereignty of data are some things that must first be dealt with⁽⁵⁾. The advancement of technology is regulated by policymakers so that socioeconomic considerations, nefarious use of AI, and economic development balance out. The adoption of AI in government activities and public services has raised ethical issues of significant concern, particularly regarding accountability and transparency. According to the Guidelines of Ethics on Trustworthy AI of the European Union, all AI systems are required to be interpretable, lawful, and non-discriminatory. Sadly, there is a lack of trust and transparency surrounding the multi-governmental utilizations of AI⁽⁶⁾.

Implementing AI for Sweden's Public Employment Service, or PES, is a relevant example of how innovation can be applied in the public sector, while also revealing important questions regarding transparency on AI. Self-optimization of the AI algorithms increases resource allocation and streamlines administrative processes, but still leaves issues like algorithmic transparency, the accountability gap, and machine bias unaddressed⁽⁷⁾. To ensure social trust within society, there is a necessity to manage the responsible deployment of AI technology in the most delicate decisions that concern the public. There needs to be an approach that manages human oversight and control while using the technology so that the society on the receiving end is well informed.

With the emergence of AI-supported Decision Support Systems (DSS), companies are starting to change their high-level decision-making processes. After AI was supported in formulating strategies, managing risks, and conducting competitor analysis, it became fundamentally involved in the processes. However, the overreliance on AI, the lack of explainability of the algorithms, and algorithmic biases are problematic. Be that as it may, organizations that are cautious and know how to use AI technologies have proven beneficial for any careful. It is possible to automate tools with AI over low to moderate-risk tasks. Future research should examine the impact of ROI trusting AI technology tools in organizational governance and management, and the score should⁽⁸⁾ also examine the impact of trusting AI technology tools for higher levels of organizational governance and management. Numerous studies have proven the successful implementation of Artificial Intelligence and machine learning. These technologies have been applied across various domains, which underscores their utility. The increasing use of these technologies demonstrates attempts to address sophisticated challenges and enhance productivity⁽⁹⁾. The literature section outlines and reviews the existing research to assist the objectives of the study. The methods subsection states the procedures undertaken for the research and the information collection techniques employed. The results of the analysis are combined with the rest of the findings. A final summary of the primary deliberations and the sequence of answers provided to the questions is captured in the concluding section.

Companies still face many unresolved problems, even though AI technology has grown increasingly useful over time. Business companies employing AI technology report positive growth in their innovative activities as well as increases in revenue, but the adoption rate for NPD is still considerably lower than other AI business applications. Low adoption is caused by

organizational readiness gaps, cost factors, and high AI project failure ratios. Indeed, the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) to the analysis and optimization of macroeconomic indicators is a new development within the domain of economics. Innovation from Within: With External Competitions, focus primarily on the new technologies, which are arguably the most important. This is because AI research significantly reduces the information asymmetry problem, which facilitates resource mobilization for global economic stabilization.

The impact of AI as a tool for economic integration and globalization is, as previously stated, intricate.⁽¹⁰⁾ CUTC showed how AI, if improperly handled, might exacerbate inequalities in economies, an issue that increasingly characterizes the BRICS digital fracture. There is no economic neutrality of AI; its impact is solely dependent on the conditions under which AI is integrated into the national economic system. Something similar is analyzed concerning ML forecasting of some known vulnerabilities in emerging markets with poorer algorithms for higher risk predictive outcomes. As⁽¹¹⁾ noted, AI equally influences every aspect of industrial innovation. This is because the digitization of economic systems is already a dominant phenomenon, and in these economies, the AI industry should be compulsory, not optional.

It is very common now to see the implementation of AI and machine learning in policymaking, and it changes the way countries develop their economic policies. AI has a widespread application in many branches of finance, particularly in ML for risk assessment, portfolio management, and market forecasting. Apart from the finance domain, AI can greatly improve the processes of macro policy formulation by automating data analysis. As highlighted by⁽¹¹⁾, AI's role in sustainable energy projects is addressed with the use of contextual topic modeling and content analysis to find patterns in vast data collections.

The adoption of AI technologies in industries and management practices is expected to result in improved productivity and creativity. The⁽¹²⁾ noted that "Industry 4.0" refers to the shift toward an advanced robotic ecosystem, which is both highly intelligent and integrated. AI integration is one of the most important facilitators of this change, owing to its ability to perform intelligent data analytics, which is complex and derives relevant information from big data sets. AI technology is capable of automatically controlling business processes through predictive analytics, which is essential in anticipating changes in the market and dealing with potential risks⁽¹³⁾. Importance is also given to the business strategy developed through pattern AI can be analyzed as⁽¹⁴⁾, strengthening the argument for the value of data and decision-making. Predictive analytics enables firms to make good business decisions that will result in efficiency in business operations due to the ability to anticipate specific scenarios in the future⁽¹⁵⁾.

When it comes to the adoption of AI technology, it is critical to closely match economic and managerial objectives with the progression of technology⁽¹⁶⁾. They expressed how AI incorporates new business goals in an AI-centered world, such as increasing effectiveness, value, and customer satisfaction.⁽¹⁷⁾ expressed that AI's impacts are felt much deeper in the economy and society at large, where data becomes the new currency. AI implementation is associated with rapid organizational and modern data-driven managerial techniques. There is a need to modernize out-of-date management systems for AI to be most effective, which creates a working partnership between humans and AI. In any case, problems such as ethical concerns, data insecurity, and sociocultural imbalance may present themselves as new challenges due to AI adoption.

Along with other benefits, the implementation of AI technologies comes with its own set of challenges. One challenge is the widening economic gap stemming from automated systems and algorithmic discrimination. Additionally, there is a data privacy and security concern that needs stringent controls on how sensitive data is handled. Transitioning toward Industry 4.0 is a gradual process that involves the government, academia, as well as industry⁽¹⁸⁾, pointing out the need to form a governmental-businesses-researchers alliance for the effective governance of AI.

It is evident that AI has made significant improvements as far as Decision Support Systems (DSS) are concerned, as it incorporates learning systems, which help in shortening time and enhancing the accuracy of decision making. AI integrated DSS systems are preferable in strategically critical fields like healthcare, finance, associated predictive analytics, and manufacturing because they focus on readiness and risk management simultaneously⁽¹⁹⁾. The concern of trust through the utilization of False Trust and Shallow Understanding (XAI) AI in DSS is discussed on how "glass box" trust is extended to AI. The need for trust in AI applications is also acknowledged to remarking that more transparent policies on AI must be devised to deal with the known problem of reliance on technology. To mitigate the social effects of AI⁽²⁰⁾ assists in formulating legal language that helps prevent harm done to people.

As of November 2023, the latest Newsroom estimate puts a global average of 42% adoption of AI technologies in operations at behemoth firms (>1000 employees). At the forefront of adoption are India and China with 59 and 58, respectively. In contrast, Germany and the USA lagged with adoption rates of 34 and 25 percent. Evidence indicates that in early 2024, only a fractional portion of businesses, approximately 23%, reported making use of AI solutions in new product development as opposed to 13% from the previous year⁽²¹⁾.

To gain a better understanding of AI's interaction with new product development (NPD),⁽²²⁾ created a positioning map illustrating the incorporation of AI technology into the NPD cycle. This framework assigns a position to AI's input on a vertical

line, distinguishing the least (“facilitator role”) and the most creative and innovative tasks (“originator role”). The stages of integrating AI into the traditional Stage-Gate process are shown by the horizontal axis, which runs from idea creation to product launch and post-launch evaluation⁽²³⁾. The effect of AI on NPD is well known and has been documented in many accounts, especially with macro enterprises. Yet, there is evidence from a German study done in 2019, which showed 5.8% of the enterprises surveyed had adopted AI for operational activities, and only 3.5% claimed to use it for NPD. It is striking that 61% of the individuals who adopted AI in other activities managed to offer product innovations and increase sales from them. One other survey of wide reach indicated that 27% of firms utilizing AI for NPD stated that the revenue has grown between 6% to 10% and attributed this growth to AI innovation⁽⁷⁾.

Management opinion research has also studied the impact of AI on NPD. According to⁽²⁴⁾, two Chinese studies showed that the adoption of powerful IT resources and AI-powered big data analytics improved the effectiveness and quality of NPD in firms⁽²⁴⁾. Other research involving 1,410 manufacturing companies revealed that the market competitiveness AI aided in human capital accumulation and collaborative innovations. As much as is known, AI fuels innovation; what is not known is the productivity of firms. One recently completed research study argued that AI provided an increase in the ability to learn from enormous amounts of data, but the direct impact on productivity is unclear⁽²⁵⁾. A study in 2024 of powerful American and German firms showed that for NPD, the effect of AI was most positive in the acceleration of the development and testing phases, along with improved resource and time decision-making. Reasons given for its application in NPD include belief in AI, trust in its business value, and commitment from senior managers.

Although AI can offer some benefits, some challenges prevent its adoption within NPD:

1. Organizational Readiness: While welcoming AI adoption, 74% of CEOs, while only 29% of the other executives share the same opinion, illustrating a divide in the leadership spectrum. The idea of organisational readiness as a result of dynamic capabilities, the firm’s capacity to actively recognise, grasp, and transform new opportunities through “unlearning” and exploratory learning, is also understood to be a by-product of organisational readiness.
2. Lack of ROI from Integrated Aided NPD: The ROI from newly implemented AI on a long-term basis is almost impossible to guesstimate. Although expert judgments and case studies appear to have some positive spillover consequences, they still make attempts needed to substantiate the connection between the use of AI with operational or financial enhancements that seem a couple of decades out of reach.
3. Implementation of software: Adoption of AI systems come with enormous expenditures, not only because of the upfront costs that go into purchasing a software license but also due to extensive infrastructure costs, human resources, and the use of expert vendors.
4. Dwindled AI Anticipations: Studies say that the outcomes for projects that utilize AI are below standard. According to a Deloitte report, only 36% of firms using AI technology received the benefits AI is supposed to provide. More so, 87% of companies that integrated AI never moved beyond the pilot phase. Additionally, only 34% of AI pilot programs ever make it beyond the pilot stage because of an issue known as “pilot paralysis”.
5. Risk Elements: Pre-determined risks concerning AI are the generation of erroneous and non-factual AI outputs, problems concerning IP, cybersecurity threats, and non-fulfillment of different legal obligations.
6. Social Issues: The anxiety regarding job displacement is outrageously elevated, which is far more theoretical than factual. Yet, studies show the probability is high that AI will only enhance the power of human creativity rather than replace it.

However, because the classic representation models fail to reflect the social and technological aspects of AI adoption as sociotechnical systems, there are always some who criticise them. Numerous academics have embraced socio-technical structures, such as the People-Processes-Technology (PPT) paradigm, to tackle these issues. The central idea within this model is that AI adoption is not simply a technological issue, but rather the result of multiple sociological, organizational, and technological interactions or relations. A scientific hypothesis is a supposition that is tentatively accepted as fact after rigorous testing that substantiates its proposed parameters⁽²⁶⁾.

H1: The use of AI-powered data analytics is positively associated with readiness to adopt AI technology.

H2: AI use in decision support systems is associated with increased readiness to adopt AI technology.

H3: AI use in Knowledge Management increases readiness to adopt AI technology.

H4: Readiness to adopt AI technology promotes Knowledge Transformation and the use of AI.

H5: Readiness to adopt AI technology influences the adoption of data and ethical issues.

H6: Ethical issues and data adoption influence Knowledge Transformation with the aid of AI.

H7: Data adoption and ethical issues are supported by AI and data analytics.

H8: Data adoption and ethical issues are supported by AI in decision support systems.

H9: Data adoption and ethical issues are supported by AI in knowledge management.

H10: AI adoption readiness has a mediating effect on the influence of AI-driven data analytics on Knowledge Transformation (KT) through AI.

H11: AI adoption readiness partially mediates the influence of AI in Decision Support Systems on Knowledge Transformation through AI adoption.

H12: AI adoption readiness partially mediates the influence of AI adoption in Knowledge Management on Knowledge Transformation through AI.

H13: The willingness to use a particular technology is a mediating variable in the impact involving AI-driven technologies and the AI transformation of knowledge.

H14: The adoption readiness for AI and the transformation of knowledge through AI have Data Adoption and Ethical Consideration as central mediating variables.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Model

The interaction between AI-driven data Analytics (DDA), Decision Support Systems (DSS), and Knowledge Management (KM), as well as their variables and their impact on an individual's readiness to embrace AI and integrate data and knowledge with ethical concerns, are illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig 1. Research Model

Interviews were conducted with three hundred and fifty respondents across both public and private sectors. The surveys also included an email component. Out of the three hundred fifty responses received, three hundred and two valid responses were included for analysis.

2.2 Survey instrument reliability

The measurement analysis of reliability testing using Cronbach’s Alpha, which determines the internal consistency within the constructions of the elements of AI adoption and its impacts on data security, knowledge management, and decision-making, is shown in the last part. The Construct is said to have acceptable reliability if the quantifying measure value is above 0.7, with higher values indicating better internal reliabilities among items. There is a contiguous measurement of AI’s contribution to data handling and AI in decision support systems (DSS), as evidenced by the low but acceptable reliability for AI in DDA (0.8590, Five items) and AI in DSS (0.770, Five items). The categories of AI in KM (0.885, six items) and KT through AI (0.888, seven items) are distinguished as having excellent reliability because the measures of AI in the processes of knowledge creation, retention, organization, and dissemination for the improvement of organizational knowledge were accurate. Finally, the idea of evaluating an organization’s readiness to adopt AI, known as AI Adoption Readiness (AR) (0.777, 7 items), conveys validity and internal consistency. The Construct Data Security & Ethical considerations (DSEC) (0.881, 7 items) attain a high measurement of reliability, which further confirms that there are pertinent AI ethical and security issues concerning information safety.

All constructs have been found to surpass the qualifying threshold for consistency, and therefore, reliability is accepted with the assumption of the tool functioning effectively regarding various domains of AI adoption and its organizational impacts.

Table 1. Internal Structure Consistency

Constructs	Cronbach Alpha	No. of Items
AI in DDA	.859	5
AI in DSS	.771	5
AI in KM	.886	6
AI in AR	.776	7
DSEC	.881	7
KT through AI	.889	7

The responses from various age groups, as seen in Table 2, also confirm the share of much younger employees. Younger respondents, those aged 25-35 years, make up 50.5% of the workforce, and only 6% of the respondents were 45 and older. The sample group consists of 301 people, so the demographic range is representative. People aged 35-45 years make up 43.5% of the workforce. To put it differently, the proportion of respondents aged 25-35 years is much larger when compared with the respondents aged 50 and older.

Table 2. Distribution of Ages

Ages	Respondents	Percentages
Less than 35	152	50.50
35-45	131	43.50
45-55	15	5.0
More than 55	3	1.0
Total	301	100

In Table 3, respondents in specific occupations are depicted in a pie chart. As expected, the IT segments capture the responses, allowing for 58.5%. It makes up around 10.3–10.6% of the 301 respondents who are in the business, healthcare, education, and other segments.

Table 3. Industry Distribution

Department	Count
Business	32
IT	176
Healthcare	31
Education	32
Others	30

There is a clear preference for IT, according to the statistics, which implies that interest in or adoption of AI is generally stronger in this sector than in others. IT is the most challenging industry, but this almost equal ratio of non-IT responders provides a fair balance.

3 Results

The analysis in Table 4 shows that the IV(s), the enhancers (M_1 and M_2), and the outcome variable (Y) interact, with a focus on their direct and indirect relationships. The independent variables and the mediators have an R squared of 0.3430 together with the Y model. The predetermined model encompassing Y indicates that the Ivs and the mediating variables suffice to explain 34.3 percent of the variability in Y. The variance is positive, meaning that the value increases. Also, the adjusted R-value set at 0.332 makes sense in light of the predictors pointed out, corroborating the amount of variance explained.

Table 4. Regression Results

Ordinary Least Square Regression Results						
Y R squared	0.343					
Adj R squared	0.332					
F statistic.	30.76					
Prob (F-statistic)	3.80E-26					
Log-Likelihood	-297.65					
AIC	607.3					
BIC	629.5					
	Coef.	Std. error	t	P> t 	0.025	0.975
Intercept	0.942	0.24	3.93	0	0.47	1.41
X_1	0.25	0.07	3.5	0.002	0.11	0.39
X_2	0.146	0.07	1.85	0.063	-0.008	0.3
X_3	0.011	0.03	0.28	0.775	-0.06	0.08
M_1	-0.0009	0.07	-0.01	0.99	-0.14	0.14
M_2	0.3078	0.07	3.94	0	0.15	0.46
Omnibus	106.122	Durbin Watson	1.434			
Prob	0	Jarque Bera	372.52			
Skew:	-1.521	Prob(JB)	1.28E-08			
Kurtosis	7.532	Cond. No	50.4			
Indirect Effects:						
X_1 → M_1 → Y: 0.0715						
X_2 → M_1 → Y: 0.2201						
X_3 → M_1 → Y: 0.0011						
X_1 → M_2 → Y: 0.297						
X_2 → M_2 → Y: 0.2227						
X_3 → M_2 → Y: 0.0306						
Summary:						
	Model	R squared	P value			
0	IVs → M_1	0.4761	0			
1	IVs → M_2	0.6044	0			
2	IV(s) and Mediators on Y	0.3435	0			
3	IV(s) on Y (Direct Effects)	0.3088	0			

The validity of the model, which has F of 30.760 and a P value of 0.0000, provides further support for the aforementioned premise that some components strongly explain Y. Regarding the predictors, X₁ has a coefficient of 0.2500 with a p value of 0.001 which states that X₁ contributes to Y and confirms that X₁ positively and productively impacts Y. Therefore, it is expected that an increase in X₁ by 1 leads to an increase of 0.25 in Y when other factors remain constant. On the other hand, X₂ has a marginal p value of 0.064 and a coefficient of 0.1464, indicating a positive but weak direct effect on Y. It is X₃ that obtains zero direct effect or has a very minimal direct effect of 0.0112 (p = 0.774), which means the outcome of X₃ on Y is statistically unimportant or quite small. M₂ is amongst the moderating variables which has a coefficient of 0.3078 (p = 0.000) which indicates M₂ has a strong effect on Y and therefore substantiates M₂ is one of the most significant variables in the mediation of the impact of IVs on Y. M₁ on the other hand has a coefficient of -0.0009, p = 0.990, which statistically means M₁ has no significant effect on Y. This permits us to conclude that M₁ does not mediate the influence that IVs have on Y.

The newly discovered results broaden the contours of the phenomenon surrounding the remote effects brought about by the involvement of moderators M₁ and M₂. M₂'s mediation consequences are the highest in the patterns X₁ → M₂ → Y (0.297) and X₂ → M₂ → Y (0.2227). This implies that M₂ serves as a mediator of X₁ and X₂ with respect to Y. In this scenario, X₂ → M₁ → Y (0.2201) also indicates a considerable degree of mediation via M₁, even though M₁ was shown not to have an impact on Y. The remaining mediational X₃, which is considered to have independent standing, seems to limit the remaining impacts: M₁ → Y (0.0011) and M₂ → Y (0.0306) residual. This indicates that X₃'s ability to predict Y by utilizing the M₁ and M₂ mediators is insufficient.

In this model, relationships were studied using the equations of IVs to the Y format. The output showed that X₁, X₂, and X₃ do not mediate or moderate and therefore explain 30.88% of the variance in Y, which was reflected in the R-squared of 0.3088. This implies that without any significant mediators, the amount of variance captured in the model is decreased to 34.3%, an amount which M₂, in particular, adds substantial value to the model's accuracy. M₁ exerts virtually no effect on Y, indicating an absence of direct proportion. One may not go wrong in claiming that Y is the outcome variable in this case. On the other hand, M₂ and Emerge both interact and directly influence X₁ and Y. The major point to be drawn from the results is that independent variables can exert some influence on the dependent variables through indirect means, and not all effects are captured by a direct measure. The findings were corroborated by comparing them to previous research, which highlighted both supportive and opposing viewpoints. The model's predictive capability supports its statistical importance. Novel conceptions were contextualized within existing frameworks to enhance their theoretical and practical contributions.

4 Conclusion

This research describes the incorporation of AI automation in business analysis, decision-making systems, and macroeconomics modeling, and highlights the effects of AI accuracy, operational efficiency, and strategic firm decision-making. AI analytics has a responsibility in business processes, as the regression results prove once again. However, 'business willingness to cognitively and physically assimilate and execute AI technologies' and 'substantive ethics towards the application of AI technology' are new constructs and two of the innumerable critical mediating variables to the AI knowledge transformation (KT) processes. Results confirm the assumption that an Agile approach to strategy concerning AI technology adoption is fundamentally important to governance and policymaking intended to optimize the claimed benefits of modern AI technologies for different sectors. The combined model of independent factors and mediators explains 34.35% of the variation in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.3435$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting a significant predictive effect. These premises assume the interface of AI technologies with their essence, at-hand preparedness, and ethics of knowledge transformation. An organization is ready to adopt AI technology for efficiency in Artificial Intelligence Data Analysis, AI Decision Support Systems, and Knowledge Management. Such systems assist organizations in improving decision-making, resource management, and innovation. The responsibility and ethical governance of data is generated from the transformation of knowledge that the organizational AI adoption Readiness creates. These factors make ethical responsibility for accountability and trust in AI systems even more important. The idea that ethical data usage regulations and "preparedness for AI adoption" serve as a link between AI adoption, knowledge transformation, and systematic integration of AI is supported by the mediation effects. The evidence gathered points to a lack of governance regulations regarding the ethical and legal boundaries of AI adoption, as well as the necessity of finding a balance between the responsible and successful integration of AI technology across industries. This study proposes the notions of organizational preparation and ethical responsibility as key mediators in the adoption and integration of AI technology. It also emphasizes the significance of strategic agility and regulatory alignment in achieving effective knowledge transformation with AI.

References

- 1) Ikram A, Jalil MA, Ngah AB, Khan AS, Iqbal T. Offshore Software Maintenance Outsourcing: Predicting Client's Proposal using Supervised Learning. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*. 2021 02;10(1):106–113. Available from: <http://www.warse.org/IJATCSE/static/pdf/file/ijatcse151012021.pdf>.
- 2) Wu M, Kozanoglu DC, Min C, Zhang Y. Unraveling the Capabilities That Enable Digital Transformation: A Data-Driven Methodology and the Case of Artificial Intelligence. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*. 2021 10;50:101368. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S147403462100121X>.
- 3) Muneer S, Ghazal TM, Alyas T, Raza MA, Abbas S, et al. Explainable AI-Driven Chatbot System for Heart Disease Prediction Using Machine Learning. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*. 2024;15(12). Available from: <http://thesai.org/Publications/ViewPaper?Volume=15&Issue=12&Code=ijacsa&SerialNo=27>.
- 4) Saba CS, Ngepah N. The Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Employment and Economic Growth in BRICS: Does the Moderating Role of Governance Matter? *Research in Globalization*. 2024 06;8:100213. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2590051X24000224>.
- 5) Janssen M, Brous P, Estevez E, Barbosa LS, Janowski T. Data Governance: Organizing Data for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence. *Gov Inf Q*. 2020 07;37(3):101493. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0740624X20302719>.
- 6) Lee MH, Chew CJ. Understanding the Effect of Counterfactual Explanations on Trust and Reliance on AI for Human-AI Collaborative Clinical Decision Making. *Proc ACM Hum Comput Interact*. 2023 09;7(CSCW2):1–22. Available from: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3610218>.
- 7) corporate author McKinsey. The State of AI in 2023: Generative AI's Breakout Year. 2023. Available from: <https://www.mckinsey.com/quantumblack>.
- 8) Naz NS, Abbas S, Khan MA, Hassan Z, Bukhari M, Ghazal TM. Optimizing Semantic Error Detection Through Weighted Federated Machine Learning: A Comprehensive Approach. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*. 2024 01;11(1):150–160. Available from: <https://www.science-gate.com/IJAAS/2024/V11I1/1021833ijaas202401018.html>.
- 9) Ghazal TM, Janjua JI, Abushiba W, ud D Iqbal MS, Iqbal W, Ahmad M, et al. Deep Learning and CNN-Based Approach for Efficient Detection of Potato Leaf Diseases. In: 2024 IEEE Asia-Pacific Conference on Geoscience, Electronics and Remote Sensing Technology (AGERS). IEEE. 2024;p. 75–79. Available from: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10932871/>.
- 10) Korinek A, Stiglitz JE. Artificial Intelligence and Its Implications for Income Distribution and Unemployment. *The Economics of Artificial Intelligence*. 2021;p. 349–390. Available from: <http://www.nber.org/chapters/c14018>.
- 11) Saheb T, Dehghani M, Saheb T. Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Energy: A Contextual Topic Modeling and Content Analysis. *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems*. 2022 09;35:100699. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2210537922000415>.
- 12) Akhtar S, Aftab S, Ali O, Ahmad M, Khan MA, Abbas S, et al. A Deep Learning Based Model for Diabetic Retinopathy Grading. *Sci Rep*. 2025 01;15(1):3763. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-87171-9>.
- 13) Saeed NMSE, Ibrahim A, Ali L, Al-Dmour NA, Mohammed AS, Ghazal TM. Unveiling the Landscape of Machine Learning and Deep Learning Methodologies in Network Security: A Comprehensive Literature Review. In: 2024 2nd International Conference on Cyber Resilience (ICCR). IEEE. 2024;p. 1–7. Available from: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10533066/>.
- 14) Hassan Y, Ghazal TM, Yasir S, Al-Adwan AS, Younes SS, Albahar MA, et al. Exploring the Mediating Role of Information Security Culture in Enhancing Sustainable Practices Through Integrated Systems Infrastructure. *Sustainability*. 2025 01;17(2):687. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/2/687>.
- 15) Al-Shallakh MAI. Embedding Artificial Intelligent Applications in Higher Educational Institutions to Improve Students' Pronunciation Performance. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*. 2024 06;14(6):1897–1906. Available from: <https://tpls.academypublication.com/index.php/tpls/article/view/8283>.
- 16) Owida HA, Hassan MR, Ali AM, Alnaimat F, Sharah AA, Abuwaida S, et al. The Performance of Artificial Intelligence in Prostate Magnetic Resonance Imaging Screening. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*. 2024 04;14(2):2234. Available from: <https://ijece.iaescore.com/index.php/IJECE/article/view/33947>.
- 17) Ghazal TM, Janjua JI, Abbas S, Fatima A, Saleem M, Khan MA, et al. Fuzzy-Based Weighted Federated Machine Learning Approach for Sustainable Energy Management with IoE Integration. In: 2024 Systems and Information Engineering Design Symposium (SIEDS). IEEE. 2024;p. 112–117. Available from: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10534747/>.
- 18) Mion G, Adauì CRL, Bonfanti A. Characterizing the Mission Statements of Benefit Corporations: Empirical Evidence from Italy. *Bus Strategy Environ*. 2021 05;30(4):2160–2172. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/bse.2738>.
- 19) Dickinson H, Teltsch DY, Feifel J, Hunt P, Vallejo-Yagüe E, Virkud AV, et al. The Unseen Hand: AI-Based Prescribing Decision Support Tools and the Evaluation of Drug Safety and Effectiveness. *Drug Saf*. 2024 02;47(2):117–123. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s40264-023-01376-3>.
- 20) Mittelstadt B, Russell C, Wachter S. Explaining Explanations in AI. *ACM Trans Inf Syst*. 2019;37(4):1–37. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287560.3287574>.
- 21) Singla A, Sukharevsky A, Yee L, Chui M, Hall B. The State of AI in Early 2024: Gen AI Adoption Spikes and Starts to Generate Value. 2024. Available from: <https://www.mckinsey.com/quantumblack>.
- 22) Cooper RG, McCausland T. AI and New Product Development. *Research-Technology Management*. 2024 01;67(1):70–75. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/08956308.2024.2280485>.
- 23) Cooper RG. The AI Transformation of Product Innovation. *Industrial Marketing Management*. 2024 05;119:62–74. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0019850124000464>.
- 24) Tan F, Zhang Q, Mehrotra A, Attri R, Tiwari H. Unlocking Venture Growth: Synergizing Big Data Analytics, Artificial Intelligence, New Product Development Practices, and Inter-Organizational Digital Capability. *Technol Forecast Soc Change*. 2024 03;200:123174. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0040162523008594>.
- 25) Babina T, Fedyk A, He A, Hodson J. Artificial Intelligence, Firm Growth, and Product Innovation. *J financ econ*. 2024 01;151:103745. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0304405X2300185X>.
- 26) Fedak KM, Bernal A, Capshaw ZA, Gross S. Applying the Bradford Hill Criteria in the 21st Century: How Data Integration Has Changed Causal Inference in Molecular Epidemiology. *Emerg Themes Epidemiol*. 2015 09;12(1):14. Available from: <https://ete-online.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12982-015-0037-4>.